

A Study on Service Quality of Online Tourism with Special Reference to Thoothukudi Area

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Abstract

The purpose of websites in the tourism industry was to provide travel information operators hoped to boost their business via. The internet, and with the low costs and lack of time and location restrictions of the internet as well as 24 hours service abundant tourist information, and resources from related business, they created a new way of consumption. Searching for travel related information is one of the most popular online activities and travellers are expected to increasingly take advantage of such content. The challenges of identifying attracting and retaining customers in the online market is becoming a critical success factor. Service quality is a judgement of customers or clients regarding overall performance of the service of the organisation and its services. The customers of today assign due weightage to the amenities and facilities they are made available while using the service. So the online tourism providers render quality of services and satisfy tourist's needs and wants and thereby retain the customers .

Introduction

Tourism sector is the second largest foreign exchange earner in India. To intensify competition in e –commerce, website service quality has become a determining factor of success in e – commerce. Initially, the purpose of websites in the tourism industry was to provide travel information operators hoped to boost their business via. The internet, and with the low costs and lack of time and location restrictions of the internet as well as 24 hours service abundant tourist information, and resources from related business, they created a new way of consumption. The quality of website service exerts a direct impact on the trust and satisfaction of consumers and is also critical to the success of this industry.

Statement of the Problem

Every industry is involved in online sales and the hospitality and tourism industry is no exception. Searching for travel related information is one of the most popular online activities and travellers are expected to increasingly take advantage of such content. Indeed, a growing use of online travel referrals through the internet individuals can make their thoughts and opinions easily available to a global community of internet users and a growing number of users actively takes advantages of this opportunity. The challenges of identifying

attracting and retaining customers in the online market is becoming a critical success factor. Hence the study was undertaken on the “A Study on services quality of online tourism with special reference to Thoothukudi area.

Objectives of the Study

The main objectives of the study are

1. To know the socio-economic profile of the respondents.
2. To identify the purpose of choosing online tourism.
3. To find out the service quality of online tourism providers.
4. To analyse the problems faced by the consumers.
5. To find out suitable suggestions.

Methodology

The study is based on both the primary and secondary data. The sample size was selected as 120. They were selected at random by applying convenience sampling method. Gap model is used to find out the service quality of Online Tourism.

Analysis and Interpretation of Data

The data are analysed in this part

Personal Profile of the Respondents

The personal profile of the respondents are described in Table 1

Table 1 Profile of the Respondents

S.No.	Profile	No. of Respondents		Percentage
1	Gender	Male	74	62
		Female	46	38
2	Age	Below 30	47	39
		30-40	33	28
		40-50	25	20
		Above 50	15	13
3	Marital Status	Married	77	64
		Unmarried	43	36
4	Monthly Income	Below Rs.20000	29	24
		Rs.20000-Rs.40000	38	32
		Rs.40000-Rs.60000	31	26
		Above Rs.60000	22	18
5	Tourist Spot	Within India	66	55
		Outside India	54	45

As observed from the Table 1 that out of 120 respondents, 62 percent of them are male, 39 percent of the respondent respondents belong to the age group of below 30 years, 64 percent of the respondents are married, 32 percent of the respondents have the monthly income of Rs.20000-Rs. 40000 and 55 percent of the respondents visit the tourist spot within India.

Purpose of Tour

The purpose for which the tourists visit the tour shown in the following

Table 2

S.No	Purpose of Tour	No. of Respondents	Percentage
1	Enjoyment	24	20
2	Relaxation	38	32
3	Business oriented	30	25
4	Celebration of holidays	28	23

Source: Primary data

It is clear from the Table 2 that out of 120 respondents, 32 percent of the respondents visit the tour for the purpose of 'Relaxation', 25 percent of the respondents visit the tour for the purpose of 'Business oriented', 23 percent of the respondents visit the tour for the purpose of 'Celebration of holidays' and 20 percent of the respondents visit the tour for the purpose of 'Enjoyment'.

Hence, the majority of the respondents (32 percent) visit the tour for the purpose of 'Relaxation'.

Service Quality of Online Tourism Services

Service quality is a judgement of customers or clients regarding overall performance of the service of the organisation and its services. Primary, service quality focuses. Primarily, service quality focuses on how online tourism meet the expectations of the customer. The essence of service quality is a measure of, how the level of delivery of service matches expectation of customer. Quality thus, it is some how interrelated with customer's satisfaction

Parasuraman, et al developed a 22 times services quality scale in which the ten original determinants of quality were collapsed into five dimensions, namely,

1. Tangibility
2. Reliability
3. Responsiveness
4. Assurance
5. Empathy

The difference between expected and perceived score of the service quality factors are given in Table 3

Table 3 Consolidated Results of GAP Model

S.No	Service Quality Factors	Expected Score	Perceived Score	Gap Score
1	Tangibility	8.13	6.09	2.04
2	Reliability	9.95	9.03	0.92
3	Responsiveness	11.01	9.11	1.9
4	Assurance	14.88	12.07	2.81
5	Empathy	14.19	10.65	3.54

Table 3 shows the gap score for the service quality of online tourism for the service quality factor 'Reliability' was low indicating the high fulfilment of the expectation of the respondents as compared to other service quality factors like responsiveness, Tangibility, Assurance and empathy.

Problems Faced

The tourists faced many problems while availing the service. The researcher enquired about the problem faced in online tourism by the respondents and it is shown in the Table 4.

Table 4 Problem Faced

S. No	Problems	Garrett Mean Score	Rank
1	Charging high amount	49.16	VI
2	No prompt ness in service	49.56	V
3	Inadequate transport facility	49.76	IV
4	Language problems	62.83	I
5	Insufficient accommodation	53.55	II
6	Tasteless food	51.08	III
7	No consideration of personal difficulties	47.6	VII
8	No privacy and security	44.33	VIII
9	Poor guidelines of tourist guide	4.21	IX

Source: Primary data

Language problem is the prime most problem faced by majority of the respondents.

Suggestions

1. The online tourism providers have a good website to attain the target online tourist successfully on the website.
2. On the tourism website, the tourism provider present Complete information about the tourism product at low cost.
3. The online tourism service provider keep the website up to date and interesting and update the content's regularly.
4. The website have a good quality photos and video, good and attractive design and have informative complete and attractive content.
5. Online booking is a major sales channels for tourism, a key element of online booking system is online payment. The online tourism service provider accept several type of online payment like card payment, bank transfer mobile payment etc.

Conclusion

Infrastructural facilities no doubt contribute significantly to the process of quality generation which focuses on the availability of infrastructural facilities to the service generating organisations. The customers of today assign due weightage to the amenities and facilities they are made available while using the service. So the online tourism providers render quality of services and satisfy tourist's needs and wants and thereby retain the customers .

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